

Synthesis, characterization and pharmacological studies of novel isocoumarins derived from two anti-inflammatory drugs – Diclofenac and Aceclofenac

Gangadhara Angajala^a, Ayyakannu Arumugam Napoleon*^a and F. Nawaz Khan^b

^aPharmaceutical Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : napoleonaa@gmail.com; aanapoleon@vit.ac.in

^bOrganic and Medicinal Chemistry Research Laboratory, Organic Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : Two novel isocoumarins 3-{2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one and (1-oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl 2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate were synthesized using two anti-inflammatory drugs Diclofenac and Aceclofenac by conventional heating. The compounds were prepared by dissolving the starting material of the non steroidal anti-inflammatory drug with THF and the corresponding acid chloride formation is done using thionyl chloride followed by condensation reaction of acid chlorides with homophthalic acid. The synthesized compounds were successfully characterized by FT-IR, Mass, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. The compounds were evaluated for pharmacological studies such as antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant and *in vitro* anti-inflammatory. Results showed promising antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria* species. Synthesized compounds also showed good antioxidant, *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activities when compared to that of standard.

Keywords : Isochromen-1-one, Diclofenac, Aceclofenac, *in vitro* anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antioxidant.

Introduction

Inflammation is generally a body's protective mechanism to remove harmful stimuli which includes damaged cells, irritants or pathogens thereby initiating the healing process. It is a fundamental pathologic process consisting various active complex of histological cytotoxic changes, cellular infiltration and release of mediators in response to tissue injury in affected blood vessels and adjacent tissues. Presently used non-steroidal anti-inflammatory COX-II inhibitors have the risk of acute myocardial and other serious coronary heart diseases. Though numerous effective anti-inflammatory agents are available it is still there is a need to develop more effective and less toxic therapeutic agents to treat the signs and symptoms of acute inflammation and long-term consequences of chronic inflammatory diseases and especially effective in the hindrance of free radical-associated damage¹.

Isochromen-1-ones are natural polyphenolic compounds found in a wide variety of plant species² with potential

therapeutic properties including some isoquinoline alkaloids³⁻⁵, antifungal^{6,7}, cytotoxic^{8,9}, antimicrobial activity¹⁰ and antimalarial effects¹¹. Diclofenac and Aceclofenac are non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs used in the treatment of numerous musculoskeletal complaints, rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, inflammations and dental pain¹². By inhibiting bacterial DNA synthesis these drugs also exhibit bacteriostatic activity. They have principle mechanism of action by inhibiting arachidonic acid cascade via an effect on enzyme cyclooxygenase. In recent years various methods have been reported for the synthesis of isochromen-1-one such as, electrophilic aromatic substitution, cyclization of 2-allyl- and alkenylbenzoic acid, palladium catalyzed reactions etc. Basavanag *et al.*, have reported preparation of 3-substituted isothiochromen-1-ones from 2-(mercaptocarbonylmethyl)benzothioic acid and various aliphatic aromatic acid chlorides¹³. Le Bras *et al.*, have reported synthesis preparation of 3-aryl-substituted isocoumarins by using *p*-toluenesulfonic acid as a mild acid catalyst under mi-

crowave irradiation for the annulation of various functionalized diarylalkynes¹⁴.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The isochromen-1-ones **3**, and **6** derived from two anti-inflammatory drugs Diclofenac and Aceclofenac were synthesized successfully. The compound 3-{2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one, **3** as synthesized was confirmed using ¹H NMR spectra showing 15 protons in which 12 protons are aromatic and ¹³C NMR spectra showed 22 carbons in which the carbonyl group of isocoumarin showed a peak at 168.81 ppm and the mass spectra further confirmed the molecular peak ion at *m/z* 395.99 (Actual mass = 396), FT-IR spectra shows absorption peak at 1737.74 cm⁻¹ for the existence of lactone ring. The existence of C-Cl peak was observed at 761.73 cm⁻¹, and the corresponding -NH stretching is observed in the region of 3406.13 cm⁻¹. In the ¹H NMR spectrum, compound **3** showed -NH peak at δ 4 ppm and the peak at δ 6.93 ppm is the characteristic peak of C₄-proton of the isochromen-1-ones ring. The compound (1-oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl 2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate, **6** as synthesized was confirmed using ¹H NMR spectra showing 17 protons in which 12 protons are aromatic and ¹³C NMR spectra showed 24 carbons in which the carbonyl group of isocoumarin showed a peak at 163.41 ppm and the mass spectra further confirmed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 454.00 (Actual mass = 454), FT-IR spectra shows absorption peak at 1756.78 cm⁻¹ for the existence of lactone ring. The existence of C-Cl peak was observed at 787.34 cm⁻¹, and the corresponding -NH stretching is observed in the region of 3427.17 cm⁻¹.

Spectral data :

3{2-[(2,6-Dichlorophenyl)amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one (**3**) : 78% yield; m.p. 170 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3406.13 (NH), 1737.74 (lactone), 761.73 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (500 MHz) (DMSO) : δ 2.34 (2H, s), 4.0 (1H, s), 6.03 (1H, s), 6.34 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 6.50 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 6.81 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 6.82 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.35 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 7.51 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 7.55 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 8.08 (2H, d, *J* 9 Hz); ¹³C NMR (500

MHz) (DMSO) : δ 166.52, 138.43, 134.63, 134.28, 132.97, 132.89, 129.70, 129.58, 129.50, 127.90, 127.49, 124.40, 127.49, 125.40, 125.32, 113.58, 113.43, 110.28, 73.97, 55.19, 40.24, 40.04, 39.20, 39.00; *m/z* : 395.9 [M] found.

(1-Oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl 2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate (**6**) : IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3427.17 (NH), 1758.7 (lactone), 787.34 (C-Cl); ¹H NMR (500 MHz) (DMSO) : δ 1.64 (1H, s), 4.23–4.24 (1H, s), 4.0 (1H, s), 6.31–6.37 (2H, m), 7.26–7.28 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 7.33–7.36 (2H, q), 7.37–7.38 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 7.44–7.46 (4H, t, *J* 10 Hz), 7.64–7.67 (2H, t, *J* 10 Hz); ¹³C NMR (500 MHz) (DMSO) : δ 173.94, 173.01, 168.81, 143.17, 136.87, 134.84, 132.82, 132.43, 132.39, 130.97, 130.85, 130.22, 129.81, 128.34, 127.56, 125.53, 124.99, 123.43, 108.99, 40.39, 39.43, 39.26, 39.10, 35.53; *m/z* : 454 [M] found.

General procedure for the synthesis of 3{2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one (**3**) :

A mixture of Diclofenac (2.8 mmol) and thionyl chloride (6 ml) were taken in round bottom flask to this 8 ml of THF was added and kept for reflux for 1 h. Completion of the reaction was determined by the absence of SO₂ gas liberation. Removal of excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure afforded to 2-(2-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetyl chloride, **2**. To the compound **2** (3.3 mmol) a mixture of homophthalic acid (1 mmol) was added and kept in oil bath at 200 °C for 4 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC using petroleum ether and ethylacetate (3.6 : 0.4). The unreacted homophthalic acid was removed by adding saturated solution of sodium carbonate (200 ml) to the reaction mixture and ethyl acetate was added. The organic layer was separated and purified by column chromatography.

General procedure for the synthesis of (1-oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl-2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate (**6**) :

A mixture of Aceclofenac (3.0 mmol) and thionyl chloride (8 ml) were taken in round bottom flask to this 8 ml of THF was added and kept for reflux for 1 h. Completion of the reaction was determined by the absence of SO₂ gas liberation. Removal of excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure afforded to 2-chloro-2-oxoethyl

2-(2-(2-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate, **5**. To the compound **5** (3.5 mmol) a mixture of homophthalic acid (1 mmol) was added and kept in oil bath at 200 °C for 4 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC using petroleum ether and ethyl acetate (3.6 : 0.4). The unreacted homophthalic acid was removed by adding saturated solution of sodium carbonate (200 ml) to the reaction mixture and ethyl acetate was added. The organic layer was separated and purified by column chromatography.

Pharmacology :

The two isochromen-1-ones **3** and **6** were successfully screened for its pharmacological activities, such as *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activity by using membrane stabilization of RBC and proteinase inhibitory efficacy, antioxidant and antibacterial activity. The present study revealed that compound 3-{2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one, **3** and compound (1-oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl 2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate, **6** possess good anti-inflammatory, antioxidant activity with an IC₅₀ of 46.74 and 50.21 for compound **3** and **6** when compared against standard ascorbic acid. The compounds also possess good antibacterial activity especially against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*.

Experimental

Chemistry :

Solvents and reagents were commercially sourced and used without further purification. Thin layered chromatography (TLC) was performed on preparative plates of

silica gel. Visualization was made with iodine chamber. Column chromatography was performed by using silica gel (100–200 mesh). The NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance III-500 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts δ in ppm).

The synthetic strategy leading to the compounds **3**, **6** are illustrated in Fig. 1. The isochromen-1-one, 3-{2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one, **3** was prepared by dissolving Diclofenac **1** in THF and the corresponding acid chloride formation is done by using thionyl chloride followed by condensation reaction of acid chlorides, **2** with homophthalic acid, **2a**. The isochromen-1-one, (1-oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl 2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino)phenyl)acetate, **6** was prepared by dissolving Etodolac **4** in THF and the corresponding acid chloride formation is done by using thionyl chloride followed by condensation reaction of acid chloride, **5** with homophthalic acid, **2a**.

Antioxidant assay :

DPPH method :

The different concentrations (10 μ g/ml, 50 μ g/ml and 100 μ g/ml) of compound **3**, **6** was prepared by using ethanol (AR). To the 3 ml of the different concentrated sample solution 1 ml of DPPH solution was added and kept in dark for 30 min at room temperature. The absorption was measured by using UV spectrophotometer (Shimadzu) at 490 nm, BHT was used as standard. For the control absorption blank sample containing the same amount of ethanol and DPPH solution was measured.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of isochromen-1-ones.

Table 1. DPPH antioxidant activity and percentage inhibition of standard and compound **3**, **6**

Sr. no.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	I% (Std ^a)	IC ₅₀	I% (3)	IC ₅₀	I% (6)	IC ₅₀
1.	10	23.10		8.01		12.77	
2.	50	60.18	39.81	37.84	46.74	42.40	50.21
3.	100	90.30		84.41		86.23	

^aAscorbic acid.**Table 2.** Membrane stabilization of RBC and proteinase inhibitory efficacy of standard and compounds **3**, **6**

Sr. no.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Inhibition for compound 3	% Inhibition for compound 6	% Inhibition for Std ^a
Membrane stabilization of RBC				
1.	25	32.10 \pm 1.01	22.19 \pm 0.47	41.18 \pm 1.33
2.	50	40.45 \pm 1.18	40.31 \pm 1.08	70.81 \pm 1.43
3.	100	75.27 \pm 1.42	54.30 \pm 1.33	86.24 \pm 0.86
Proteinase inhibitory efficacy				
1.	25	30.24 \pm 0.81	23.16 \pm 2.12	36.74 \pm 0.17
2.	50	53.86 \pm 0.16	35.20 \pm 0.17	64.32 \pm 1.12
3.	100	73.42 \pm 1.48	52.91 \pm 1.22	81.67 \pm 0.19

^aEtodolac.**Table 3.** Antibacterial activity of compound **3**, **6** and standard

Strains	Zone of inhibition for Std ^a (mm) (30 μg)	Zone of inhibition (mm)					
		Sample 3			Sample 4		
		10 μg	20 μg	30 μg	10 μg	20 μg	30 μg
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	16	6	7	12	3	7	10
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	12	5	6	7	4	7	9
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	11	3	6	9	4	8	10

^aAmpicillin.

The experiment was carried out in triplicate (Table 1).

In vitro anti-inflammatory studies :

In the present work *in vitro* anti-inflammatory studies were carried out by two methods such as membrane stabilization test and proteinase inhibitory test according to the method described by Paschapur *et al.*¹⁵. The results were summarized in Table 2.

In vitro antibacterial studies :

Screening of antibacterial activity was carried out by standard disc diffusion method. Test compounds were dissolved in DMSO. 7 mm Whatmann no. 1 filter paper discs impregnated with different concentration of the test sample were mounted on the surface of inoculated plates. Erythromycin was taken as a standard drug. For 24 h inoculated plates were incubated at 35–37 °C. After incubation zone diameters were measured to the nearest millimeter (mm) and the values are summarised in Table 3.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have synthesized successfully two novel isocoumarins namely 3-{2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)-amino]benzyl}-1*H*-isochromen-1-one, **3** and (1-oxo-1*H*-isochromen-3-yl)methyl 2-(3-((2,6-dichlorophenyl)-amino)phenyl)acetate, **6** using Diclofenac and Aceclofenac as starting materials. The compounds showed promising antimicrobial activity especially against *Bacillus subtilis* and good antioxidant, *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activities. The presence two active potent moieties in the final compound makes it biologically more stable with high therapeutic efficacy. In future extensive research has to be carried out to evaluate the anti-inflammatory efficacy and toxicity studies of novel isocoumarins synthesized in the present work.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank the management of VIT

University, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India for their constant encouragement and support and providing all the necessary facilities for carrying out this study.

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